

Project Title	Expanding FAIR solutions across EOSC
Project Acronym	FAIR-IMPACT
Grant Agreement No.	101057344
Start Date of Project	2022-06-01
Duration of Project	36 months
Project Website	FAIR-IMPACT

D6.3 - MoU and SLA templates for data interoperability

Work Package	WP6 - Interoperability
Lead Author (Org)	Salomé Landel (CNRS)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Suzanne Dumouchel (CNRS), Olivier Rouchon (CNRS), Jérôme Pansanel (CNRS), Liisa Marjamaa-Mankinen (CSC), Lassi Lager (CSC), Emilie Kraaikamp (KNAW DANS), Deborah Thorpe (KNAW DANS), Kevin Ashley (UEDIN/DCC), Joy Davidson (UEDIN/DCC), Agnes Jasinska (UEDIN/DCC), Sandra Boerman (DTU/DeiC), Anne Sofie Fink - (DTU/DeiC), Renato Juacaba Neto (EMBL EBI), Liise Lehtsalu (RDA), Matti Heikkurinen (RDA; CODATA), Giacomo Cannizzaro (SURF), Esteban González Guardia (UPM)
Due Date	2025.01.31
Date	2025.01.30
Version	V1.0

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Author	Notes
0.1	2023.11.28	Salomé Landel (CNRS)	TOC and V0.1
0.2	2024.05.30	Salomé Landel & Olivier Rouchon (CNRS), Liisa Marjamaa-Mankinen (CSC), Emilie Kraaikamp & Deborah Thorpe (KNAW DANS), Kevin Ashley & Joy Davidson (UEDIN/DCC), Anne Sofie Fink & Sandra Boerman (DTU/DeiC), Renato Juacaba Neto (EMBL EBI), Esteban González Guardia (UPM)	Development of the Chapter and first draft of appendix 3.
0.3	2024.06.30	Salomé Landel (CNRS), Esteban González Guardia (UPM)	Update of Chapters and development of appendices.
0.4	2024.10.11	Suzanne Dumouchel, Olivier Rouchon & Jérôme Pansanel (CNRS), Liisa Marjamaa-Mankinen & Lassi Lager (CSC), Emilie Kraaikamp & Deborah Thorpe (KNAW DANS), Kevin Ashley, Joy Davidson & Agnes Jasinska (UEDIN/DCC), Renato Juacaba Neto (EMBL EBI), Anne Sofie Fink & Sandra Boerman (DTU/DeiC), Liise Lehtsalu (RDA), Matti Heikkurinen (RDA & CODATA), Giacomo Cannizzaro (SURF), Esteban González Guardia (UPM)	Collective reviews of previous sections and appendices.
0.5	2024.11.15	Salomé Landel (CNRS)	Executive summary, introduction and conclusion added. Test results added. Harmonisation of the deliverable and appendices.
0.6	2025.01.15	Mark Van de Sanden (SURF), Jessica Parland-von Essen (CSC)	External review
0.7	2025-01-29	ALL	Address external review points

Disclaimer

FAIR-IMPACT has received funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe funding programme for research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement no. 101057344. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

Table of content

INDEX - Tables and Figures	4
Terminology	4
Executive Summary.....	6
Introduction	7
1. Introduction to SLA and MoU.....	8
1.1 SLA: standards and implications	8
1.2 MoUs standard structure.....	12
2. Data interoperability standards to be included in SLAs and MoUs	14
2.1 Recommendations for legal interoperability.....	16
2.2 Recommendations for organisational interoperability	19
2.3 Recommendations for semantic interoperability.....	22
2.4 Recommendations for technical interoperability.....	25
3. SLA and MoUs for data interoperability.....	29
3.1 SLAs for data interoperability	29
3.2 MoUs and data interoperability.....	36
Conclusions and next steps.....	40
Appendix 1: Guidelines to develop SLA on data interoperability - based on FitSM	41
Appendix 2: Guidelines to develop MoU on data interoperability.....	47
Appendix 3: Other data interoperability contracts.....	50

INDEX - Tables and Figures

Figure #1: Overview of the SLM Framework according to FitSM	9
Table #1: recommendations on the legal context of the service provider.....	17
Table #2: recommendations on data access and reuse.....	17
Table #3: recommendations on metadata format	18
Table #4: recommendations on licences	19
Table #5: recommendations on agreements.....	20
Table #6: recommendation on terminologies	22
Table #7: recommendations on the use of Semantic artefacts.....	23
Table #8: recommendations on security and privacy framework	26
Table #9: recommendations on access to data sources	27
Table #10: recommendation on search tools	28
Table #11: recommendation on PID	28
Figure #2: Data production, sharing and use - stakeholders analysis	29
Table #12 - Recommendation on methodology	31
Table #13 - classification of results.....	31
Table #14: Results - Service component - Metadata schema format.....	32
Table #15: Results - Service component - Metadata schema content	32
Table #16: Results - Metadata schema used	33
Table #17: Results - Semantic artefacts.....	33
Table #18: Results - Metadata and data format	34
Table #19: Results - clauses integrated in the respondents' MoUs.....	37
Figure #3: mapping hypotheses for MoUs for data interoperability.....	38

Terminology

Terminology /Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
ARIA	Access to Research Infrastructure Administration
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DSA	Data Sharing Agreement

Terminology /Acronym	Description
DTR	Data Type Registry
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud/European web of FAIR data and related services for research
EOSC-IF	EOSC Interoperability Framework
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
FitSM	family of standards for lightweight IT service management
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding, pl. Memoranda
MSCR	Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry
OLA	Organisational Level Agreements
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RI	Research Infrastructure
RIOXX	Research Output Metadata Schema
RO-Crate	Research Object Crate
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SA(s)	Semantic Artefact(s)
SMS	Service Management System
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SLM	Service Level Management
SLS	Service Level Specifications
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SSSOM	Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
ToU	Terms of Use
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

Executive Summary

This deliverable, produced by Work Package 6 (interoperability) of the FAIR-IMPACT project, examines how MoUs and SLAs could promote data interoperability within the EOSC Federation.

In the context of EOSC, data interoperability depends on all four interoperability dimensions: Legal, Organisational, Semantic and Technical. Research data repositories, as intermediaries between data producers (researchers) and data users, are identified in this deliverable as central to establishing and maintaining data interoperability as a service (section 3.1).

SLAs and MoUs should be used as tools to enhance all levels of interoperability. An SLA is a written document that defines the expected level of service and outlines specific metrics, responsibilities and remedies to ensure accountability between service providers and users / customers. Conversely, an MoU is an agreement between parties that outlines their mutual intentions, roles and shared objectives, creating legally binding obligations (may be very limited effects) for parties. These agreements can enable more user-centred and efficient service and process development. Including data interoperability in relevant documents or if feasible writing separate documents would be important to take interoperability forward.

While both types of agreements clearly enhance organisational interoperability by enabling stakeholders to align business processes towards common goals, there is currently a significant gap in accessing and harmonising all the guidelines to support interoperability in the legal, semantic and technical dimensions. Today, the evolving EOSC federation lacks a robust, community-endorsed framework for systematically describing and enforcing data interoperability, highlighting the need for such guidelines.

Given this lack of compliance to common standards, the considerable diversity of service providers (with over 500 providers registered in the previous EOSC portal) and the EOSC's transition to a federation, the provision of standard templates for agreements is premature. A fundamental step before developing agreements is to assess the capacity of the organisations involved to inform the development of effective agreements.

Rather than providing agreement templates, this deliverable proposes recommendations and guidelines to help service providers self-assess their capabilities and thus enable them to design agreements that are appropriate to their specific capabilities. The guidelines in the appendices support the development of SLAs and MoUs for data interoperability by providing structured recommendations that offer both a model for drafting agreements and the flexibility to adapt to different contexts.

Introduction

Interoperability¹, the central focus of Work Package 6 in the FAIR-IMPACT project, is a cornerstone for realising the vision of the EOSC: to create a web of FAIR data and services for science in Europe². This deliverable examines how MoUs and SLAs can contribute to improving data interoperability within this framework.

Data interoperability is defined by the OECD as "*the capacity to combine and use data from disparate digital tools with ease, coherence and efficiency*"³. It enables data services and products to be stored, processed, shared, and recombined in different formats and locations, promoting seamless integration and reuse. As the research process in general transcends services, systems and organisations, and research data might stem from many sources, the researcher can easily be troubled by interoperability issues.

Despite progress in the EOSC ecosystem, significant challenges remain in harmonising and ensuring data interoperability. The lack of unified actionable guidelines and standardised materials has resulted in a lack of concrete, cross-domain, community-endorsed standards for achieving interoperability across legal, organisational, semantic and technical dimensions.

SLAs and MoUs emerge as interesting tools in this context. By their very nature, MoUs and SLAs are key tools for organisational interoperability, as they describe working processes that allow stakeholders with different business processes to work together.

SLAs provide a framework between a provider and a customer for defining service delivery, helping providers to articulate service guarantees and giving users a clear understanding of service expectations. MoUs, on the other hand, are strategic agreements that bring together stakeholders with common goals, making them ideal for fostering collaboration within communities. While SLAs focus on service delivery, MoUs are used to align broader strategic interests.

In order to examine the role of MoUs and SLAs in promoting data interoperability, this deliverable is divided into three sections. The first section defines and analyses the nature, purpose and structure of SLAs and MoUs. The second section examines the four dimensions of data interoperability - legal, organisational, semantic and technical - and identifies mechanisms for their implementation. The final section suggests scenarios where SLAs or MoUs could support data interoperability. In addition, the appendices provide practical guidelines to assist readers in developing their own SLA or MoU tailored to their context of data interoperability.

¹"The ability of computer systems or software to exchange and make use of information."

² European Commission. European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) [online]. European Commission, [n.d.] [viewed November 11, 2024]. Available at: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

³ OECD. *OECD Digital Education Outlook 2023* [online]. OECD Publishing, 2023. [Accessed 3 December 2024]. Available at: https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/education/oecd-digital-education-outlook-2023_12f8ebe3-en

1. Introduction to SLA and MoU

This chapter introduces the standards for and implications of SLAs and MoUs. Each has a different purpose in defining and managing expectations, responsibilities, and standards between different parties:

- **An SLA is service-specific: it is a formalised document that describes how a service is provided and sets out the expectations and obligations of both parties involved in a service relationship.**
- **An MoU covers broader context than only service provisioning or delivery: it outlines the intentions and roles of the parties involved in a collaborative effort. An MoU can be synonymous with a roadmap, a shared future vision.**

At the end of the deliverable, appendix n°3 lists additional agreements that can be signed in the context of data sharing.

1.1 SLA: standards and implications

1.1.1 Introduction to SLAs

In the international information technology context there are various frameworks for IT service management. In this document we refer to FitSM which is a family of standards for lightweight IT service management.⁴ FitSM is free and produced with EU funding, while others such as ITIL⁵ are not.

FitSM sees SLAs as part of a broader IT management tool: the Service Level Management (SLM) framework.⁶ As part of SLM, FitSM recommends maintaining a service catalogue, establishing and periodically reviewing SLAs for all services, monitoring service performance against defined targets, and establishing and monitoring Organisational Level Agreements (OLAs)⁷ for services or service components provided by different teams of service providers (independent internal units for instance).

The SLM framework includes the Service Catalogue and the SLA in the same process, to improve and maintain the quality of the IT services provided, while continually aligning the needs of the community with the capabilities of the organisation.

The diagram below illustrates the structure of the Service Level Management (SLM) framework:

⁴FitSM [online] - [n.d.] [viewed October 31,, 2024]. Available at: <https://www.fitsm.eu/>

⁵ITIL: Information Technology Infrastructure Library: <https://www.itlibrary.org/index.php?page=ITIL>

⁶FitSM. Collection of CC-BY 4.0 templates [online]. FitSM, [n.d.] [viewed October 31, 2024]. Available at: <https://www.fitsm.eu/downloads/#toggle-id-5>

⁷“Operational Level Agreement - OLA” as a non-legal SLA equivalent (allows IT departments to achieve “meeting of the minds” without committing organisations in ways that would require discussions with the legal departments)

Figure #1: Overview of the SLM Framework according to FitSM

The overall aim of an SLA is to clearly define the expectations and obligations of providers and users/customers in writing, facilitating a transparent and fair service relationship. SLAs specify the criteria for service quality and how it is measured, particularly through metrics such as service availability, frequency of service failures, time to restore the service, response time and user feedback. If the Service Description is short and concise, it can be written into the contract. Otherwise, the contract usually refers to the attached service description. SLAs play a key role in risk management of the contract.

In some scenarios, there is a distinction between a general document describing service levels and the document describing the service levels to be provided to a particular customer/user. In these scenarios, the general document is described as a Service Level Specification - SLS - and the SLA is a variant of this which is specific to one customer. The SLS will generally be open; the SLA may not be. In this deliverable, SLA refers to both.

Vocabulary: Customer vs. User – In the context of this deliverable, there is ongoing debate over whether to use the term "customer" or "user" as the counterpart in an SLA. This reflects differing perspectives among service providers within the EOSC framework. For some organisations, most research services are offered free of charge, and users are not necessarily considered customers. For others, services are paid for, meaning users become customers by virtue of their financial contribution.

In certain cases, organisations may pay for a service (thus becoming the customer), but the individuals who ultimately benefit from the service are the users. These distinctions highlight the complexity of defining roles within the EOSC context.

This issue remains unresolved in this deliverable, as it is recognised that not all services within the EOSC framework involve payment.

Regarding the legal dimension of SLAs, three different scenarios have been identified:

- **SLAs with detailed guarantees:** in some cases, SLAs function as stand-alone legal documents that are enforceable in their own right. Failure to meet the agreed service

levels can result in legal action against the service provider, as the SLA itself can be prosecuted.

- **SLAs as contract extensions:** SLAs can also be added to legally binding contracts. In this context, they become "contract extensions" that may include provisions for rewards or penalties. For example, if a service provider fails to meet agreed service levels, it may be required to refund some or all of the customer's money
- **Best effort SLAs:** SLAs can also take the form of statements of intent or plans to maintain a certain level of service quality. In such scenarios, some elements of the SLA are based on a 'best efforts' approach, meaning that there is no guarantee that the service will be delivered or that it will meet certain quality standards.

Which type of an SLA is needs to be clarified in the SLA document itself or the contract it extends.

Example #1: in the academic context, where reputation is relational, it may be more important to publicly state the level of service than to have a strict penalty clause.

Example #2: local labour laws or organisational policies prevent a 24/7 support staff coverage. Thus, the technical service may be available 24/7, but help desk service and problem analysis or service recovery (beyond what is accomplished by automatic tools) will be limited to standard office hours.

However, even in the case of commercial providers, the penalty clauses fall considerably short of compensating potential damages due to failures of mission-critical applications.

Example: Amazon's approach is to provide service credits to reduce costs for the services user in the billing period following the SLA failure⁸. Microsoft uses a similar approach⁹.

The above does not mean that SLAs do not impact service quality. However, the impact does not seem to be primarily tied to fear of financial repercussions of service failure. Rather, the benefits are more likely due to factors such as:

- Analysis of the dependencies between service components which is a prerequisite for realistic service level targets in the SLAs;
- The reputation of the service provider being linked to reaching specific service targets;

⁸ Amazon Web Services. AWS Service Level Agreements [online]. Amazon Web Services, [n.d.] [viewed October 31, 2024]. Available at: https://aws.amazon.com/legal/service-level-agreements/?aws-sla-cards.sort-by=item.additionalFields.serviceNameLower&aws-sla-cards.sort-order=asc&awsf.tech-category-filter=*all

⁹ Microsoft. Service Level Agreements (SLA) for Online Services [online]. Microsoft, [n.d.] [viewed October 31, 2024]. Available at: <https://www.microsoft.com/licensing/docs/view/Service-Level-Agreements-SLA-for-Online-Services?lang=1>

- Awareness of the “goal posts” both in the customer and in the service provider organisations.

1.1.2 SWOT analysis of SLAs

The SWOT analysis of SLAs shows that they bring significant benefits to both the user / customer and the service provider. However, this added value often comes at a cost.

One of the key strengths of SLAs is their **ability to clearly define mutual expectations between service providers and customers/users**. In addition to describing the service, SLAs outline not only the quality and availability of the service, but also what the provider expects from the customer/user. This up-front clarity promotes effective communication and builds trust, as customers/users can rely on the provider's documented commitments.

SLA provides an extra layer of protection. If the provider fails to meet the agreed terms, the customer/user has a basis on which to seek compensation (which is described in the SLA). Conversely, if the customer/user's expectations exceed what is outlined in the SLA, the provider can use the document to clarify its responsibilities. This can open the door to negotiation and the creation of a bespoke SLA that offers enhanced service levels tailored to the customer/user's needs, accompanied by mutually agreed valuations or compensatory measures.

Because SLAs are usually part of a wider SLM process: they are subject to monitoring and evaluation of results, along with performance audits at defined review periods. This **systematic approach facilitates continuous service improvement**, which drives innovation for providers. Innovation in this context can include improving service quality, reducing production costs, increasing customer/user satisfaction and extending market reach to new customers/users.

Continuous improvement not only enhances competitiveness by building trust in the service provider, as mentioned above, but also ensures that services meet users' needs increasingly better over time.

At the same time, **the implementation of SLAs introduces complexity for service providers**, which can be seen as a weakness in several respects. Firstly, **SLAs impose a degree of rigidity on service delivery**. Providers commit to a certain quality of service that is outlined in the document. If unforeseen problems arise (such as staff absence or equipment failure), the provider may not have the flexibility to temporarily adjust the quality of service to address the problem. Thus, SLAs should clearly define force majeure situations (such as suspected security breaches) and procedures for managing other exceptional situations, including the method and timeframe for resolution.

Secondly, this complexity requires considerable preparatory work by the supplier, including documenting and analysing services to determine how they are framed into an SLA. **This preparatory phase, together with the measures required to ensure a consistent service level, incurs costs for the service provider**. These costs are manifested in terms of staff time spent on developing the SLA, as well as any additional effort or investment required to maintain service standards in the event of unforeseen disruptions. In addition, the SLA needs to go through legal review, therefore also legal expertise is required.

Finally, SLAs pose different types of risks. As mentioned above, documenting service levels in a contract inhibits service improvement. **This limitation is particularly apparent in digital services, where technology is advancing rapidly and SLAs quickly become outdated.** In fast-evolving landscapes, it may be beneficial to have SLAs with shorter durations or frequent updates (yearly basis) to remain competitive. In addition, they should not be too specific on technical details, leaving room for suppliers to adapt.

It's important for customers / users to understand that the impact of SLAs on the provider is limited in case of a breach of the SLA. If the service provider fails to meet the objectives outlined in the SLA, there may be no legal or financial consequences. However, even though some SLAs are not legally binding, failure to meet them can still damage a provider's reputation.

In summary, SLAs help to tailor services more closely to user needs and to structure an organisation's service delivery system. While this has positive effects, there are potential risks to consider. Providers must carefully assess their capabilities to develop an SLA that accurately reflects the level of service they can consistently deliver. **By conducting a thorough analysis at the outset, these risks can be mitigated or avoided altogether.**

1.2 MoUs standard structure

1.2.1 Introduction to MoUs

An MoU is an agreement **between two or more parties that expresses their intention to formalise a collaboration, outlining mutual responsibilities and shared objectives.** MoUs cover a wide range of issues and are flexible enough to **cover general and strategic intentions** rather than precise service-related commitments. They are less technical than SLAs and can serve as the basis for future legal contracts more binding, helping the parties to establish a collaborative framework and align their overall objectives. MoU and SLA can also be complementary to each other: MoU on how parties are collaborating and SLA describing the service levels under which services are being provided in the collaboration.

An MoU defines the role and responsibilities of each party, helping to minimise future disputes and avoid duplication of effort. It sets out key details such as the duration of the agreement, key dates, cost responsibilities and associated financial arrangements. In addition, MoUs can provide clarity on the governance structures within certain partnerships.

Although typically written as a non-binding agreement, an MoU can contain binding clauses in certain areas. For example, it may outline obligations relating to confidentiality, intellectual property rights or commitments to formalise a legal contract in the future. This flexibility allows MoUs to act as a practical tool to promote collaboration while addressing key legal and operational considerations.

1.2.2 SWOT of MoUs

The SWOT analysis of MoUs reveals significant benefits, including improved knowledge sharing, better resource optimisation and enhanced collaboration. However, it also identifies key challenges such as complex negotiations, up-front costs and potential security risks. By effectively managing these challenges, organisations can capitalise on the opportunities of formalised business relationships while minimising the risks.

The strength of an MoU lies in its primary purpose: to clearly define the responsibilities of each party. By documenting the actions of each participant, along with any relevant appendices, the MoU ensures transparency and accountability. This clarity is critical to fostering effective collaboration, preventing conflict and enabling performance measurement. It also helps to build trust, allocate resources appropriately and ensure the continuity of the project. These elements are fundamental to the success and long-term sustainability of the partnership and its objectives.

Implementing an MoU can be a complex task, as it requires careful drafting to **avoid ambiguity and vague language in defining the responsibilities of each party.** One of the main weaknesses of MoUs is the potential for confusion over their legally binding nature. If the document does not clearly state which provisions are legally binding and which are not, this can lead to conflicting interpretations and a lack of clarity about the enforceability of the terms.

To avoid such problems, the **MoU should explicitly state which terms are binding and which are not.** Legal professionals, such as lawyers, are usually responsible for drafting the MoU to ensure that the document is clear and legally sound. As an expression of goodwill, MoUs may also include mitigation provisions, such as prompt notification of issues and a remediation plan, to address potential concerns and ensure smooth cooperation.

The opportunities associated with MoUs relate to increased collaboration and optimisation of each party's resources. In the context of service providers, MoUs play a critical role in promoting data integration and the adoption of common standards to ensure compatibility, quality and efficiency across systems and processes. This alignment facilitates interoperability, improves communication, reduces errors and fosters a collaborative environment. In addition, **MoUs help to build trust between stakeholders, encourage innovation and strengthen partnerships for long-term success.** By formalising mutual intentions and shared goals, MoUs create a foundation for continuous improvement and growth within the collaborative framework.

There are a **number of potential risks associated with MoUs, mainly due to their limited legal protection.** This lack of enforceability can create ambiguity and uncertainty about the binding nature of the agreement, making it difficult to resolve disputes, ensure accountability and protect the interests of the parties involved.

In addition, an MoU can be difficult to implement, particularly when it comes to avoiding vague or imprecise language that could lead to future misunderstandings or conflicts. **To mitigate these risks, it is essential that the MoU is carefully drafted, with clear definitions of the parties' responsibilities and the binding nature of certain provisions.**

In conclusion, MoUs are valuable tools for formalising collaborative efforts, ensuring clear communication, optimising resources and managing risks. They provide a flexible yet structured approach to partnerships, fostering mutual understanding and paving the way for successful, sustainable collaborations. **The non-legally binding nature of MoUs, coupled with their adaptability, makes them particularly popular in scientific contexts, where they are often respected and upheld by the community.** Although they do not provide the same legal protection as formal contracts, MoUs remain an effective mechanism for aligning the interests and objectives of different stakeholders.

2. Data interoperability standards to be included in SLAs and MoUs

In the context of EOSC, the backbone of interoperability is the EOSC-IF (European Open Science Cloud Interoperability Framework)¹⁰. It breaks down interoperability into four key categories: legal, organisational, semantic and technical.

The EOSC-IF is a written document designed to be open and adaptable, with the aim of lowering barriers to entry for both users and providers¹¹. **Interoperability standards are often dynamic, evolving in response to the specific context in which data are shared and reused.** Given the diversity of scientific fields, each with its own policies and practices, it is challenging to create a universal set of standards that can address all the nuances of data interoperability. **A one-size-fits-all approach may not meet the different needs of each domain.** This diversity limits the feasibility of integrating the standards and recommendations outlined in the EOSC-IF into rigid, formal documents such as MoU and SLA templates.

In the future, as the technical requirements for data interoperability within the EOSC framework become more detailed¹², they will directly influence the design of SLAs and MoUs for data interoperability within the EOSC community. One of the key developments in this space is the drafting of the EOSC Federation Handbook¹³. At the time of writing this document, the draft of the first half of the handbook has been published, covering primarily high-level governance and operational architecture issues. Once the build-up phase of the EOSC federation will be more advanced, the goal is to refine and provide foundations for the MoUs and SLAs that can be used to codify the relationship between the EOSC nodes as well as between resource providers and the EOSC nodes their resources are onboarded into.

¹⁰ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K., Ojsteršek, M. et al., *EOSC interoperability framework – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

¹¹ EOSC Future. Inventory of Core Functions and Inclusion Criteria [online]. December 2021 [viewed October 31, 2024]. Available at: <https://eoscfuture.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/EOSC-Future-WP2-EGI-D2.5a-Inventory-of-Core-Functions-and-Inclusion-Criteria-2021-12-03.pdf>

¹² Scardaci Diego Orazio, Sciacca Eva, Hériché Jean-Karim, Van De Sanden Mark, Klaas Wierenga, Manghi Paolo, Tamburri Damian, Mazon Jose Norberto, López García Álvaro, Hugo Wim, Pansanel Jerome, & Krøl Andersen Lene. (2023). A landscape overview of the EOSC Interoperability Framework - Capabilities and Gaps (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8399710>

¹³ EOSC Federation Handbook [online]. EOSC Association, [Accessed 3 December 2024]. Available at: <https://eosc.eu/eosc-federation-handbook/>

In the absence of fully defined technical requirements at this stage, this chapter proposes some initial technical applications of data interoperability that could serve as a basis for these agreements. These preliminary considerations will help to develop a step-by-step approach outlining the key elements to be considered when drafting an SLA or MoU focused on data interoperability.

In order to define what is at stake here, it is important to clarify the term 'research data':

The term “research data” refers to the evidence used to inform or support research conclusions. The EOSC Glossary defines research data as *“data collected or produced in the course of scientific research activities and used as evidence in the research process, or commonly accepted in the research community as necessary to validate research findings and results.”*¹⁴

Research data may include various forms, such as raw data, research ready, published output datasets of published catalogue-type presentations of published output datasets and it may also be divided into categories, such as observational, experimental, simulation, divided/compiled, and reference/ canonical.

Examples of research data: documents, spreadsheets, laboratory notebooks, fieldnotes, diaries, questionnaires, transcripts, codebooks, audiotapes, database contents, etc.

The interoperability recommendations selected in this context focus specifically on the ability to move and reuse data with clear context and without unnecessary barriers - i.e. data interoperability. This focus excludes other types of interoperability, such as those related to the compatibility of software and IT systems with each other. While some recommendations within the EOSC-IF may apply to both contexts, the aim here is to provide a more detailed understanding and definition of data interoperability.

Data interoperability: *is the capacity to combine and use data from disparate digital tools with ease, coherence and efficiency.*¹⁵

Using this framework, **the chapter identifies data interoperability requirements that could shape the development of SLAs and MoUs.**

The recommendations in this chapter are grouped into two main areas:

¹⁴ DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/1024 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast), modified — reference to data.)) Sources: https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/EOSCPartnershipMF_Glossary.pdf (EOSC glossary also in Zenodo and was in the marketplace - what's the future..?)

¹⁵OECD. *OECD Digital Education Outlook 2023* [online]. OECD Publishing, 2023. [Accessed 3 December 2024]. Available at: https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/education/oecd-digital-education-outlook-2023_12f8ebe3-en

- For service providers: guidance on how to describe and implement data services that ensure data interoperability.
- Agreement format: advice on how to design SLAs and MoUs that are accessible and promote data interoperability.

2.1 Recommendations for legal interoperability

2.1.1 Introduction to legal interoperability and EOSC-IF recommendations

Legal interoperability refers to *‘the ability to combine datasets from multiple sources without conflicts among restrictions imposed by the license of each dataset’*.¹⁶ It also concerns cases where access to data *‘is restricted or subject to conditions’* in which case the conditions for access and use should be *‘clearly and readily determinable through automated means’*, and they should *‘not conflict with each other’*.¹⁷

This section considers what would be required of service providers to achieve legal interoperability. Some of the criteria and recommendations can be acted upon directly by service providers, whilst others have stronger implications for the work of data providers (i.e. the data depositor/owner, researcher/data collector) and/or the EOSC Federation itself and other actors.

Having set out the criteria and recommendations, it is possible to suggest a list of statements for use in future agreements. However, it should be noted that rather than being a set of *requirements*, the commitments below are presented as something for the service provider to work towards.

2.1.2 Recommendations on the legal context of the service provider

In the European context of the EOSC, legal frameworks and policies are not yet fully aligned. It is not yet clear that all European Member States are committed to having legislation that fully allows the establishment of EOSC services within and between EU Member States. **This makes the legal context from country to country not fully interoperable, as data rules may differ from one place to another.**

¹⁶ Doldirina, Catherine & Eisenstadt, Anita & Onsrud, Harlan & Uhlir, Paul. (2018). Legal Approaches for Open Access to Research Data (p.8). <https://doi.org/10.31228/osf.io/n7gfa>. Quotation is as cited in the EOSC Interoperability Framework, p. 12

¹⁷ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K., Ojsteršek, M. et al., *EOSC interoperability framework – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

Table #1: recommendations on the legal context of the service provider

#	For whom?	Recommendations
#1	Service providers	Clarify the law applicable to the data provided, in particular to clarify the extent to which data can be reused.
#2	Service providers	The service should comply with the current European legal framework for data sharing, as well as EU contract law, competition law and applicable sectoral regulation. ¹⁸

2.1.3 Recommendations on data access and use

To ensure clarity on access terms, **it is essential to outline any restrictions on the use of shared data**. Metadata plays a crucial role in ensuring compliance with legislation, notably the GDPR. Specific mechanisms can be implemented to minimise the need for multiple permissions to access datasets, which is also linked to technical interoperability.

Some service providers, in particular data source providers, host data stored by external users. These providers cannot be held responsible for the content of the data, including its quality and any personal data it may contain.

In addition, some service providers face legal or organisational challenges regarding cross-border access to data, especially for sensitive data sets such as medical data.¹⁹

Table #2: recommendations on data access and reuse

#	For whom?	Recommendations
#3	Service providers	The access conditions and legal usage terms for each dataset made available by the service should be clearly specified using one or more well-known metadata schema elements and in a machine-readable format.
#4	Service providers	Wherever possible, offer a mechanism that allows users to request access to a set of datasets from a single data provider at once. This will reduce the time and effort spent by researchers on access requests (and therefore contribute to the Reusability of data). The data provider should then be able to grant access to the whole set through a single authorisation process - Ex: ARIA for SSH and life sciences ²⁰

¹⁸European Commission: Joint Research Centre, Farrell, E., Minghini, M., Kotsev, A., Soler-Garrido, J. et al., *European data spaces – Scientific insights into data sharing and utilisation at scale*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2023, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/400188> P69-70

¹⁹ Foggetti, N., Gerin Laslier, M., Di Giorgio, S., Haile Gebreyesus, N., Müller, S., van Nieuwerburgh, I., Romier, G., & Van Wezel, J. (2021). EOSC-Pillar D4.1 Legal and Policy Framework and Federation Blueprint. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4486610>

²⁰ARIA Services [online]. [n.d.] [viewed October 31, 2024]. Available at: <https://aria.services/>

#5	Service providers	There should be an indication of who is responsible for the content of external users' data.
#6	Service providers	Access rights to data should also be defined for users from countries other than the country of origin of the service.

2.1.4 Recommendations on metadata format

In terms of interoperability, **metadata ensures better compatibility between different systems and platforms and facilitates the exchange and integration of data**, notably by providing a standard format that is compatible between different groups. As part of FAIR-IMPACT, WP6, the DCAT metadata schema is recommended as appropriate to improve interoperability of data²¹.

Table #3: recommendations on metadata format

#	For whom?	Recommendations
#7	Service providers	Use metadata schemas that are available without restriction.
#8	Service providers	Provide appropriate metadata for the datasets they offer, using accepted standards in line with the FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable), even in cases where access to the data is restricted.
#9	Service providers	Make clear which metadata schema is used for the data shared.

2.1.5 Recommendations on licences

According to the X-Oficio study, "[...] the more the data is open, the less impediments to legal interoperability will occur. In this case, licences can be a barrier to legal interoperability, as they can restrict the reuse of data"²². **To support legal interoperability, the service provider can adopt standardised licences (e.g CC0, CC BY, PDDL)²³ and clarify in the metadata the legal and contractual (e.g. exclusion of commercial use) restrictions associated with the shared data.**

²¹ Rouchon, O., Kraaikamp, E., Gonzalez, E., Fink Kjeldgaard, A. S., Pedersen Tenderup, N., Davidson, J., Hodson, S., Rettberg, N., & Scharnhorst, A. (2024). D6.2 - Core metadata schema for legal interoperability (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11104269>

²² Graber-Soudry, O., Minssen, T., Nilsson, D., Corrales, M., Wested, J., & Illien, B. (2021). Legal Interoperability and the FAIR Data Principles (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471312>, p.31

²³ Ibid.

Table #4: recommendations on licences

#	For whom?	Recommendations
#10	Service providers	Provide clear, standardised licences for the datasets they offer, in both human-readable and machine-readable formats, if available.
#11	Services providers	Promote the use of permissive licences for metadata where appropriate (and preferably for data where possible), adopting a no-rights-reserved statement (e.g. CC0) as standard.
#12	Service providers	Ensure that the metadata includes information to identify the different components of the dataset, specifying which are subject to different copyrights or the licence under which each component is provided.
#13	Service providers	Provide a mechanism to indicate in the metadata whether copyright has expired or whether the data is already in the public domain.
#14	Service providers	Provide a mechanism to indicate in the metadata if a dataset they make available is partly or wholly made up of orphan data ²⁴ .

2.2 Recommendations for organisational interoperability

2.2.1 Introduction to organisational interoperability and its description in the EOSC-IF

Organisational interoperability: *“the way in which organisations align their business processes, responsibilities and expectations to achieve commonly agreed and mutually beneficial goals. In practice, organisational interoperability means documenting and integrating or aligning **business processes** and relevant **information exchanged**. Organisational interoperability also aims to meet the requirements of the user community by making services available, easily identifiable, accessible and user-focused.”²⁵*

The European Interoperability Framework (EIF) has two recommendations relating to organisational interoperability²⁶ :

²⁴ In the EOSC Interoperability framework, orphan data is defined as “historic copyrightable datasets and metadata which have no license or unclear licenses arrangements and where the copyright holder is unknown or not reachable”. European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K., Ojsteršek, M. et al., *EOSC interoperability framework – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>, p.24

²⁵ European Commission (n.d.) *European Interoperability Framework (EIF)*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/eif_en/ (Accessed: 29/01/2025).

²⁶ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K. et al., *EOSC Interoperability Framework – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

- Recommendation 28: document your business processes using commonly accepted **modelling techniques** and **agree on how these processes should be aligned** to deliver a European public service²⁷.
- Recommendation 29: clarify and formalise your **organisational relationships** for establishing and operating European public services²⁸.

The EOSC-IF noted that organisational interoperability was the “least-discussed” aspect of interoperability. Although many challenges were identified by those consulted, few concrete solutions exist. The EOSC-IF recommendations are based on a single, hub-and-spoke view of organisational interoperability - that sees organisations as **service providers**, data providers or service consumers interacting with EOSC’s centrally-provided services and governance structures.

2.2.2 SLAs and MoUs as key to organisational interoperability

MoUs and SLAs play a key role in enabling interoperability and **should be scalable**. Indeed, through the relationship between either service providers and users or stakeholders with common interests, they allow the documentation of business processes within a written document and explain how different business processes can be aligned. They also allow the formalisation and clarification of organisational relationships.

In a context such as that of the EOSC Federation, where stakeholders come from different organisations, from different scientific communities, providing different types of research services, **having documents that clarify how working relationships are provided, detailing and defining what is meant with technical vocabularies, is key to enabling members of the EOSC community to understand each other and work together.**

Table #5: recommendations on agreements

#	For whom?	Recommendations
#15	Agreement format	Agreements must be specific in their scope and the parties involved should be unambiguously identified.
#16	Agreement format	The agreement must clearly define the service(s) involved and/or the actions to be carried out (such as periodic data interchange). If this definition is external to the agreement, as is often the case, the agreement should specify what happens when the external definition changes.
#17	Agreement format	The agreement must clearly outline the obligations of all parties involved and provide a clear definition of each party's responsibilities.

²⁷ European Commission. Recommendation 28 [online]. Joinup, [n.d.]. Available at: <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/nifo-national-interoperability-framework-observatory/solution/eif-toolbox/recommendation-28>

²⁸ European Commission. Recommendation 29 [online]. Joinup, [n.d.]. Available at: <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/nifo-national-interoperability-framework-observatory/solution/eif-toolbox/recommendation-29>

#18	Agreement format	MoUs/SLAs must specify the duration of their validity and whether they will expire automatically if not renewed, or whether they will remain in force until cancelled by one or more parties. While these aspects are often included in formal contracts, they are often overlooked in MoUs/SLAs.
#19	Agreement format	The agreement should include an update clause which makes clear instances which may require a revision to the agreement. Consider scheduling regular reviews of the agreement (e.g., annually) to ensure that any need for revision can be identified.
#20	Agreement format	The agreement must specify the communication mechanisms between the parties (service provider, customer and end user). It should outline the technical methods for contacting the parties and the ways in which information can be exchanged.
#21	Agreement format	A translated version of the MoU/SLA service descriptions should be provided if the agreement is written in a language not common to both parties.
#22	Agreement format	SLAs should specify the availability of the service, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the hours and/or days when the service is available. • Notice periods for planned periods of unavailability and the methods for making such notices SLAs may also specify: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The average period of availability between interruptions, such as mean time between incidents or a similar measure
#23	Agreement format	The agreement should follow the FAIR principles (with a PID, in a repository, with open licence, etc.) even if it is not public.

2.2.3 Use common vocabulary and clarify terminology

Organisational interoperability among different organisations sharing data or services implies the documentation and alignment of business processes and information. A simple example from the university world is the commonality of certain job titles and roles, such as post-doctoral researcher or professor. This alignment of information (if not business processes) facilitates labour mobility between institutions and is a form of interoperability between them.

Table #6: recommendation on terminologies

#	For whom?	Recommendation
#24	Agreement format	The document should clearly define terms used with a specific meaning, either within the document itself or by referring to a common controlled vocabulary. Any controlled vocabularies commonly used should be used.

2.3 Recommendations for semantic interoperability

Semantic Interoperability is “the ability of computer systems to transmit data with unambiguous, shared meaning. Semantic interoperability is a requirement to enable machine computable logic, inference, knowledge discovery, and data federation between information systems”²⁹.

2.3.1 The role of semantic artefact catalogues

The central element to achieve semantic interoperability is the semantic artefact (SA).

Semantic artefact (SA): “Semantic artefacts are machine readable models of knowledge such as controlled vocabularies, thesauri, and ontologies which facilitate the extraction and representation of knowledge within data sets using annotations or assertions”³⁰.

Semantic artefact catalogue (SAC): “a broader term to encompass ontology repositories, registries, vocabulary/terminology services and metadata schemas catalogues”³¹.

The EOSC-IF has made a number of recommendations for improvement, and more recently the EOSC Semantic Interoperability Task Force has extended and refined some of the concepts presented in the EOSC-IF report³². However, the concept of semantic interoperability is still evolving and its implementation remains subject to different interpretations, with no single agreed approach within the EOSC community.

²⁹European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K., Ojsteršek, M. et al., *EOSC interoperability framework – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

³⁰Le Franc, Y., Parland-von Essen, J., Bonino, L., Lehvälaiho, H., Coen, G., & Staiger, C. (2020). D2.2 FAIR Semantics: First recommendations (1.0 DRAFT). FAIRsFAIR. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3707985>

³¹Jonquet, J., Graybeal, J., Bouazzouni, S., Dorf M., Fiore, N., Kechagioglou, X., Redmond, T., Rosati, I., Skrenchuk, A., Vendetti, J., Musen, M., & members of the OntoPortal Alliance (2023) *Ontology Repositories and Semantic Artefact Catalogues with the OntoPortal Technology*. The Semantic Web – ISWC 2023. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-47243-5_3

³²Nyberg Åkerström, W., Baumann, K., Corcho, O., David, R., Le Franc, Y., Madon, B., Magagna, B., Micsik, A., Molinaro, M., Ojsteršek, M., Peroni, S., Scharnhorst, A., Vogt, L., & Widmann, H. (2024). *Developing and implementing the semantic interoperability recommendations of the EOSC Interoperability Framework* (27 March 2024). EOSC Association AISBL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10843882>

The wide variety of SAs, ranging from simple vocabularies to more complex ontologies, complicates the application of the EOSC-IF. The main debates on semantic interoperability include:

- **Lack of common explicit definitions:** a common understanding of key terms is necessary for interoperability³³.
- **Lack of reference repositories with explicit governance:** in order to improve the registration and maintenance of SAs and to create user-friendly interfaces, clear governance structures need to be established³⁴.
- **Diversity of metadata schemas in different communities:** there is a need for a consensus to exchange cross-domain data and metadata and/or making (meta)data discoverable.
- **Importance of domain specificity:** developing a single standard to meet the diverse needs of different communities is complex, and community profiles may be required to manage this variability.
- **Focus on the SAs themselves:** current discussion on the fact that interoperability should be based more on the artefacts – such as vocabularies – than on their catalogues.

There are currently no EOSC projects specifically dedicated to the design of SACs as core components. To address this, the FAIR-IMPACT T6.1 team is developing a list of metrics to assess the semantic interoperability of EOSC components with the EOSC-IF as part of D6.1³⁵, which provides guidelines for interoperability. A version of these metrics and their testing with some EOSC components can be found in M6.1³⁶.

The preliminary list of metrics is as follows:

Table #7: recommendations on the use of Semantic artefacts

#	For whom?	Recommendations
#25	Service provider	Data provided should be linked to semantic artefacts.
#26	Service	The semantic artefact(s) used should be based on published, linked

³³ Jonquet, C., Gonzalez, E., Aubin, S., & Grau, N. (2024). FAIR-IMPACT project response to "DRAFT: Developing and implementing the semantic interoperability recommendations of the EOSC Interoperability Framework" (Versión V1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10874897>

³⁴ Jonquet, C., Gonzalez, E., Aubin, S., & Grau, N. (2024). FAIR-IMPACT project response to "DRAFT: Developing and implementing the semantic interoperability recommendations of the EOSC Interoperability Framework" (Versión V1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10874897>

³⁵ Deliverable to be published by the FAIR-IMPACT project in June 2025

³⁶ Outcome of testing components to achieve core technical & semantic interoperability in cross-domain use cases. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10940164>

	provider	and maintained ones and include a usage example.
#27	Service provider	The semantic artefact(s) used should have an open licence.
#28	Service provider	The semantic artefact(s) used should be well documented
#29	Service provider	The semantic artefact(s) used should be published in a repository.
#30	Service provider	The semantic artefact(s) used should be associated with a persistent identifier (PID).

2.3.2 The use of crosswalks

The use of crosswalks between domains (or within a domain) is also fundamental to align terms and enable data interoperability. They are essential for ensuring that data from various sources and systems can "talk" to each other, maintaining clarity and usability while preventing the confusion that might arise from differing terminologies and structures. Crosswalks are directional and often are contextual/domain dependent.

“Crosswalks establish relationships between elements in different models to achieve interoperability and effective data exchange, particularly when dealing with data from various domains. They involve translation, converting (meta)data from one schema to another, and promoting cross-domain (meta)data discovery. Crosswalks are typically presented in tables that align and map data across different schemas”³⁷.

While the EOSC-IF recommends the maintenance of crosswalks between different standards and ontologies, it does not provide detailed guidance on how to build, maintain and share these crosswalks, and the recommendations could benefit from greater specificity, particularly with regard to the tools (platforms and services) required to create and manage these mappings. Finally, there is a need to adopt the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings (SSSOM), which would provide a standardised, open approach to sharing ontology mappings across platforms and domains. A review of crosswalks can be found in the Appendix I of the EOSC IF document³⁸.

³⁷ Nyberg Åkerström, W., Baumann, K., Corcho, O., David, R., Le Franc, Y., Madon, B., Magagna, B., Micsik, A., Molinaro, M., Ojsteršek, M., Peroni, S., Scharnhorst, A., Vogt, L., & Widmann, H. (2024). Developing and implementing the semantic interoperability recommendations of the EOSC Interoperability Framework (27 March 2024). EOSC Association AISBL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10843882> - P.7-8

³⁸ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K., Ojsteršek, M. et al., *EOSC interoperability framework – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

The Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry³⁹ (MSCR) component, developed by the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, is a practical implementation for creating mappings between metadata schemes.

2.4 Recommendations for technical interoperability

Technical interoperability is “the ability of different information technology systems and software applications to communicate and exchange data”. The EOSC-IF complete the definition by adding “the ability to accept data from each other and perform a given task in an appropriate and satisfactory manner without the need for extra operator intervention”⁴⁰.

This definition is broad and goes beyond data sharing. In the remainder of this subsection, we will discuss some of the recommendations of the EOSC-IF, the challenges associated with them, and the tools that EOSC resources could use in the context of data interoperability.

2.4.1 A common security and privacy framework (including authorisation and authentication infrastructure)

Privacy restrictions are difficult to harmonise because they are highly specific to data providers and users. This increases the need for them to be maintained in a federated manner, where infrastructures such as EOSC act as an intermediary infrastructure, while providers and users can manage their restrictions.

Federated *authentication* is typically implemented using SAML and/or the OAuth protocol⁴¹. It allows third parties to verify and acquire user identities. This is available in large systems such as eduGAIN, AARC Blueprint Architecture, GitHub, and ORCID. For example, services can use the ORCID OAuth to verify user identities⁴².

The implementation of federated *authorisation* is more difficult because of how different stakeholders perceive access rights and privacy. Role-based authorisation is a well-used and flexible authorisation method, and will focus on it for the purposes of this document. Here, user information includes data properties such as institution association and its role within the institution, and these properties can be mapped to predefined access levels that systems check before performing actions. For example, an user with property “role” with value “owner” might allow users to modify some specific data objects.

The challenge is for different resources to respect each other's assigned roles. **This task would be greatly facilitated if resources harmonised the roles that can be assigned to users.** The EOSC federation could standardise roles, such as the owner role mentioned above, but it would be difficult to find a set of roles that all stakeholders would find applicable. In any case,

³⁹ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/metadata-schema-and-crosswalk-registry-mscr>.

⁴⁰ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K., Ojsteršek, M. et al., *EOSC interoperability framework – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649> - P. 11

⁴¹ OAuth. OAuth 2.0 [online]. OAuth, [n.d.]. Available at: <https://oauth.net/2/>

⁴² ORCID. Sign In Using ORCID Credentials [online]. ORCID, [n.d.]. Available at: <https://info.orcid.org/documentation/integration-guide/sign-in-using-orcid-credentials/>

data providers and owners should be free to control which users are assigned to which roles. This also depends on organisational interoperability: either the aim is to align job titles and roles, or to create a mapping of competences and permissions linked to the different possible roles and titles in the EOSC context.

The 2022 EOSC AAI architecture⁴³ follows the 2019 AARC Blueprint Architecture⁴⁴ which describes the entities for access management between research collaborating activities. Additionally, AARC provides guidelines⁴⁵ on how to define roles and the usage of identity protocols.

Table #8: recommendations on security and privacy framework

#	For whom?	Recommendations
#31	Service provider	When they join an infrastructure such as EOSC, they need to join its AAI federation using the OAuth protocol or a similar protocol following AARC guidelines. This allows their users to share credentials and access to services and data across the infrastructure. ⁴⁶ It also implies having a harmonised system of roles that can be assigned to users.
#32	Service provider	The service provider should describe the protective measures the service offers as default and optional or provide a security policy that describes the sensitivity of data that can be stored in this service.

2.4.2 Easy access to data sources available in different formats

As mentioned above, data shared span different communities, subjects, institutions and technologies, so **it is inevitable that they will be highly heterogeneous.**

Example: Consider the documentation of the EMBL-EBI Search Service⁴⁷. Here, the documentation is exposed in a human-readable page that explains all the endpoints and parameters used. In addition, the machine-readable OpenAPI JSON document is available. Users will find the information in readable tables and interactable elements to facilitate human understanding in addition to tags, templated paths, input and outputs in JSON format to facilitate machine parsing.

⁴³ Kanellopoulos, C., & Liampotis, N. (2023). EOSC AAI Architecture 2022. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10379293>

⁴⁴ Blueprint Architecture 2019. AARC. Available at: <https://aarc-community.org/guidelines/aarc-g045/>

⁴⁵ Guidelines for expressing group membership and role information. AARC. Available at: <https://aarc-community.org/guidelines/aarc-g069/>

⁴⁶ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Wierenga, K., Johansson, L., Kanellopoulos, C., Groep, D. et al., *EOSC Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Group (WG) Architecture AAI Task Force (TF)*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/8702>

⁴⁷ EBI Search REST API Documentation [online]. European Bioinformatics Institute, [n.d.].(Accessed October 31, 2024) Available at: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ebisearch/documentation/rest-api>

Table #9: recommendations on access to data sources

#	For whom?	Recommendations
#33	Service providers	(Meta)data should be exposed in widely used and well-documented formats (such as XML, JSON, CSV, and RDF).
#34	Service providers	The (meta)data structure should be defined using JSON schemas or XML schemas to specify fields and attributes of the data exposed. These schemas should be registered in an appropriate registry and should receive a PID. For example: FAIRCORE4EOSC's Data Type Registry ⁴⁸
#35	Service providers	Options for converting and exporting the (meta)data into these standard formats should be provided.
#36	Service providers	When exposing (meta)data in RDF, resources from trustworthy and recognised organisms such as W3C ontologies ⁴⁹ , schema.org ⁵⁰ , SKOMOS or the OntoPortal ⁵¹ should be used to ensure interoperability through publicly available terms.
#37	Service providers	Documentation of how to use API endpoints should be available. Formats such as OpenApi ⁵² are well known ways of documenting web APIs.

The FAIRCORE4EOSC project has two components that address these requisites directly. The EOSC Data Type Registry (DTR)⁵³ records data types while minting permanent identifiers for each one. The Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR)⁵⁴ addresses the translation of data from one data type to another, which in conjunction with their data type registry, would greatly assist in the definition of pipelines of data among EOSC resources.

⁴⁸EOSC Data Type Registry. FAIRCORE4EOSC. Available at: <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/eosc-data-type-registry-dtr>

⁴⁹ W3C. Lists of Ontologies [online]. W3C, [n.d.]. Available at: https://www.w3.org/wiki/Lists_of_ontologies

⁵⁰ Schema.org. Schemas [online]. Schema.org, [n.d.]. Available at: <https://schema.org/docs/schemas.html>

⁵¹ OntoPortal. About [online]. OntoPortal, [n.d.]. Available at: <https://ontportal.org/about/>

⁵² OpenAPI Specification. OpenAPI Specification [online]. OpenAPI Initiative, [n.d.]. Available at: <https://spec.openapis.org/oas/latest.html>

⁵³ FAIRCORE4EOSC. EOSC Data Type Registry (DTR) [online]. FAIRCORE4EOSC, [n.d.]. Available at: <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/eosc-data-type-registry-dtr>

⁵⁴ FAIRCORE4EOSC. Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR) [online]. FAIRCORE4EOSC, [n.d.]. Available at: <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/metadata-schema-and-crosswalk-registry-mscr>

2.4.3 Search tools for Coarse-grained and fine-grained dataset (and other research object)

Discovering relevant data across community-shared resources is necessary. Search tools must be able to query the different providers and return the useful information. However, “useful information” varies depending on the use case. Executive level users mostly query consolidated data while some users, such as researchers, may query detailed data. Supporting both types of query is essential, even if sometimes difficult to achieve. Resources must be required to have efficient and well documented search endpoints for their data.

Table #10: recommendation on search tools

#	For whom?	Recommendation
#38	Service providers	The resources must have efficient and well documented search endpoints for their data to allow harvesting and discovery of their data.

Example: The European Union’s SPARQL search page⁵⁵ is a service that offers fine and coarse search results. Through SPARQL queries, users are able to get dataset lists or aggregated information on the datasets available.

2.4.4 A clear PID Policy

Persistent identifiers are essential as they provide reliable means to reference data across resources and remove the possibility of ambiguous references.⁵⁶

Table #11: recommendation on PID

#	For whom?	Recommendation
#39	Service providers	Provide PIDs for the data associated with a detailed explanation on the PID used and the PID policy of the service.

⁵⁵ European Commission. SPARQL Endpoint [online]. European Commission, [n.d.] Available at: <https://data.europa.eu/data/sparql?locale=en>

⁵⁶ FAIR-IMPACT - D3.2 - User guidelines on EOSC PID implementation will be published before summer 2025 providing more details on the topic.

3. SLA and MoUs for data interoperability

In the context of data interoperability, the creation of MoU and SLA templates for service providers and data customers/users will enhance interoperability. Explicitly including interoperability in these documents OR producing separate interoperability SLAs would likely promote implementation of the FAIR data principles. These agreements, though not necessarily legally binding, clarify commitments in the context of working / service relationships. If the interoperability requirements are consistent across service providers offering similar services, overall interoperability will improve.

3.1 SLAs for data interoperability

3.1.1 Stakeholders and perimeter

SLAs are key documents to clarify how a service is provided and for increasing confidence in the provision of the service. In the context of this deliverable, the focus is on SLAs between research data repositories – which collect, store and curate the (meta)data –, and their customers / users, who expect the data to be interoperable so that it can be reused in another context.

Figure #2: Data production, sharing and use - stakeholders analysis

As shown in the diagram above, data repositories are recognised within the EOSC framework as key stakeholders with the greatest potential to improve data interoperability. While laboratories / scientific instruments, as primary data producers, have a direct impact on data quality, they generally lack the broader perspective and tools required to manage data at scale and do not fulfil the role of service providers. In contrast, data repositories are seen as primarily responsible for managing data and ensuring its interoperability. This responsibility is achieved by implementing appropriate data exchange protocols, defining formats that support data reuse, applying metadata standards that meet interoperability requirements, and addressing the legal and governance considerations associated with the data they share.

By facilitating access to and reuse of research data at a defined level of quality, data repositories are positioned as the primary actors likely to issue SLAs within the data interoperability landscape.

Data repositories include a broader category of service providers or research resource providers. These service providers, whether part of an EOSC or not, provide services to their users. The hypothesis presented in this deliverable is that these providers will propose SLAs to ensure the interoperability of the (meta)data they share.

In this context, the focus is on data interoperability only. This means that there is no clear expectation that the IT infrastructure should be interoperable, only that data should be formatted in such a way that it can be reused in different contexts.

Regarding the implementation of SLAs, sometimes, especially in the context of research and higher education, SLAs are made publicly available on the service provider's website without requiring signatures from both parties (service provider and customer/user)⁵⁷. Sometimes they do require signatures from both parties.

If, in the future, data interoperability SLAs are developed in the context of the EOSC federation – to bind the EOSC federation to EOSC nodes (thematic, national, etc.) – the data interoperability policies would not change much from the SLAs linking individual service providers and customers / users, as the goal would remain the same: to provide interoperable data. Some organisational requirements might be added or adapted, but the way in which data interoperability is technically implemented and described in the SLA would not evolve.

3.1.2 SLA Test results

As part of this deliverable, a test was sent to seven organisations to assess their willingness to implement SLAs for their services and the level of detail that could be described in the document to ensure data interoperability for their customers / users. **It is recognised that the results cannot be definitive as the group of organisations targeted was not large enough.**

⁵⁷ Example from CINES - accessed on 17 January 2025 - <https://www.cines.fr/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/eTDR-CINES-SLA.pdf>

Table #12 - Recommendation on methodology

#	For whom?	Recommendation
#40	Service providers	If the data interoperability SLA templates are to be implemented on a large scale, extensive test phases are recommended to propose recommendations that are not too far removed from the reality of those responsible for implementing them.

Of the seven organisations contacted, only five replied to the questionnaire. Some requested anonymity, so the results are presented accordingly. This survey targeted organisations that provide services related to data storage and access, such as data repositories.

Of the five responses received, one provide services to both individual researchers and research infrastructures (#1). Two provide services to individual researchers, research infrastructures and research performing organisations (#2 & #3). One provides services to individual researchers only (#4) and one provides services to both individual researchers and research performing organisations (#5). The number used in the tabs below helps to identify the organisation.

Table #13 - classification of results

	1	2	3	4	5
Individual researchers	x	x	x	x	x
Research infrastructures	x	x	x		
Research Performing Organisations		x	x		x

To share their services, three organisations rely solely on their own service portal to share resources (#2, #3, #4) while the other two utilise both their portal and the EOSC portal (#1, #5). One organisation charges researchers' affiliated institutions for access (#2). Another respondent provides open data access, with restricted data available upon approval (#4). Another organisation offers both open and SLA-based access (#5). Finally, access to one organisation depends on a framework agreement or affiliation with a higher education institution or national research institute(#3).

Of these five organisations, three propose SLAs based on best effort (#1, #3, #5), one an SLA based on guaranteed results (#2) and one has no SLA (#4).

In line with the above recommendations for ensuring data interoperability, the aim of the test was also to determine whether the targeted service providers were prepared to provide this level of service. The results of the test show that there are no harmonised practices to guarantee all levels of data interoperability.

The table below shows the way in which a metadata schema format could be designed and used to ensure data interoperability is not fully followed.

Table #14: Results - Service component - Metadata schema format

Service components - Metadata schema format	1	2	3	4	5
The provided datasets are accompanied by metadata	x		x	x	x
The proposed metadata schema is available without restrictions	x		x	x	x
The proposed metadata schema is machine readable	x		x	x	x
Controlled vocabularies commonly used like AGROVOC, MeSH, or GEMET are used to ensure uniform understanding of the terms used in the metadata					
The datasets and associated metadata are protected by clear, standardised, human and machine-readable licences.			x		x
Where applicable, the use of permissive licences for metadata and data, as well as no-rights-reserved statements (e.g.CC0), is the standard.			x	x	

Regarding the content of the metadata schema, as shown in the table below, the more detailed the description of the metadata, in particular with regard to legal restrictions on access and use of the data, the less it is taken into account by the surveyed service providers.

Table #15: Results - Service component - Metadata schema content

Service component - metadata schema content	1	2	3	4	5
The metadata schema attached to each dataset includes detailed information, such as the author, publication date, licence, keywords, and descriptions	x		x	x	x
The metadata schema attached to each dataset includes identification of the responsible party for the data content stored by external users	x		x	x	
The metadata schema attached to each dataset includes information to identify different dataset components subject to various copyrights or licences					
The metadata schema attached to each dataset includes details on the time limit of copyright, indicating when the data will enter the public domain				x	
The metadata schema attached to each dataset includes information on the dataset's content, specifying if it partly or fully consists of orphan data					
The metadata schema attached to each dataset includes information on access rights to data for users from a country other than the country of origin of the service					

As part of FAIR-IMPACT, deliverable 6.2, the DCAT metadata schema is recommended to improve legal interoperability thanks to structures to support legal interoperability and help machine-actionability.⁵⁸ The table below shows that none of the organisations surveyed currently use such a schema.

⁵⁸ Rouchon, O., Kraaikamp, E., Gonzalez, E., Fink Kjeldgaard, A. S., Pedersen Tenderup, N., Davidson, J., Hodson, S., Rettberg, N., & Scharnhorst, A. (2024). D6.2 - Core metadata schema for legal interoperability (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11104269>

Table #16: Results - Metadata schema used

Metadata schema used	1	2	3	4	5
Dublin Core Metadata Element Set/Terms				x	x
Datacite Metadata Schema			x	x	x
Research Output Metadata Schema (Rioxx)					
Asset Description Metadata Schema					
Open Digital Rights Language					
Data Privacy Vocabulary					
FAIRSharing Policy Schema					
Data Catalog (DCAT)					
OpenAIRE Guidelines				x	
Data Documentation Initiatives				x	
Research Object Crate (RO-Crate)					

As far as semantic artefacts are concerned, only two out of five respondents declare that the data provided is shared with semantic artefacts. Of the two, only one uses semantic artefacts that are based on existing ones (with a usage example), well documented, linked to an open licence, with a clear governance policy and published in a repository. The other organisation using semantic artefacts only ensures that they are associated with a PID.

Table #17: Results - Semantic artefacts

Semantic artefacts	1	2	3	4	5
Does data provided are linked to semantic artifacts?		Yes	Yes	No	No
The semantic artifact(s) used is based on existing ones and includes a usage example.			x		
The semantic artifact(s) used is well documented			x		
The semantic artifact(s) used have an open license			x		
The semantic artifact(s) used has a clear governance policy			x		
The semantic artifact(s) used is published in a repository			x		
The semantic artifact(s) used is associated with a persistent identifier (PID).		x			

In terms of data and metadata format, the test results show that some of the technical principles of interoperability are being followed, but again, the more a principle is detailed, the less it is being followed by the service providers tested.

Table #18: Results - Metadata and data format

Metadata and data format	1	2	3	4	5
The data is available in widely used formats, including XML, JSON and CSV	x	x	x	x	x
The data structure is defined using JSON schemas or XML schemas to specify fields and attributes.	x	x	x		x
Options for converting and exporting the data into these standard formats are provided.		x	x		
When exposing data in RDF, resources from W3C ontologies, schema.org, SKOMOS or the OntoPortal are utilised to ensure interoperability through publicly available terms.		x			

When it comes to search tools, only two out of five respondents say that all endpoints used by developers are thoroughly documented using OpenAPI or Swagger UI, and that search endpoints are linked to a user manual to support both coarse and fine-grained data discovery (#3, #5).

Regarding the use of PIDs, all respondents indicated that all shared records have a PID, but only one respondent provided details of the PID policy implemented for the service concerned (#3).

Of the five respondents, three stated that they would be prepared to provide SLAs based on best efforts to deliver the service levels stated in the questionnaire (#1, #3, #5). Three of the respondents stated that all the detailed service levels were in place today (#1, #3, #4). One stated that this would be implemented in the longer term (more than a year) (#5).

The results of this test reveal significant variability in the implementation of SLAs and data interoperability practices among the organisations surveyed. While most organisations demonstrate a commitment to certain FAIR principles, **there is a lack of harmonisation in critical areas**. These findings, while acknowledging that the panel is not large enough to draw too definitive conclusions, underscore the importance of establishing consistent SLA policies and promoting interoperability standards to better align service providers with the FAIR principles and enable more seamless data sharing across infrastructures.

3.1.2 Suggestions for implementation: step-by-step approach

Start on a best effort basis

According to the EOSC Enhance deliverable 1.4, SLAs in the EOSC context typically mean an intention or a roadmap for service quality rather than a rigid guarantee.⁵⁹ This perspective is reinforced by the EOSC Pillar study which indicates that the current approach of service providers is based on trust and best efforts, suggesting that enforceable agreements may not yet be practical.⁶⁰ The same results can be seen from the test carried out for this deliverable.

In relation to establishing the EOSC Federation, a certain level of interoperability should be

⁵⁹ Appleton, O. (2020). D1.4 EOSC Portal SLA, SRM, Privacy Policy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13619185>

⁶⁰ Foggetti, N., Gerin Laslier, M., Di Giorgio, S., Haile Gebreyesus, N., Müller, S., van Nieuwerburgh, I., Romier, G., Van Wezel, J., Hönegger, L., Bodlos, A., & Vernet, M. (2021). Legal and Policy Framework and Federation Blueprint. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5647948>

established through the EOSC Federation Policies, Rules and criteria to join the Federation. This needs to be detailed in the EOSC Federation Handbook. The second step, when joining the EOSC Federation requires signing a Federation Agreement or MoU, the policies, rules, criteria and other obligations and responsibilities need to be described in the Agreement/MoU. Next step, this can be defined in a SLA between provider and customer, as in a legal binding document.

With this in mind, **a first approach could be to use best-effort SLAs in the short term.** This approach would encourage service providers to strive for the specified service levels without putting them under undue pressure. In the medium to long term, these SLAs could evolve into more binding commitments. This gradual evolution is intended to build confidence within the user community and give service providers sufficient time to adapt their services to meet these expectations. They may also continue to be best-effort based.

Data interoperability framework

Currently, there are no established, centralised and harmonised technical standards for implementing data interoperability within the EOSC Federation. Existing guidelines tend to be either overly broad, lacking in technical specificity, or narrowly focused on specific domains. **There is no consensus among the wider service provider community on minimum technical guidelines that would ensure data interoperability across domains.** This lack of standardised guidance complicates the development of this deliverable and will challenge future SLAs in describing data interoperability requirements.

Without such clear, community-endorsed guidelines, implementation efforts are open to different interpretations, leading to inconsistent levels of data interoperability across communities. This inconsistency is particularly problematic for the development of SLA templates, which require a description of the service scope, dependencies associated with service delivery, service level targets and performance metrics. If interoperable data is the core service, then a comprehensive definition of data interoperability at all relevant levels is essential. Without an initial and precise standard for implementing data interoperability, identifying dependencies, setting service level targets and defining performance metrics will remain challenging and ambiguous.

More defined guidelines are under development in the context of the EOSC federation.⁶¹ It is envisaged that some of these will be domain specific. The results of this work will greatly increase the capacity to feed future SLAs on the subject.

Finally, the current transitional phase of the EOSC limits the ability to identify which body will be responsible for what in the future. The responsibility for data interoperability may evolve in the future. This will have an impact on future SLAs in this area.

Guidelines to develop SLA on data interoperability

The development of a template SLA is not feasible as they need to be tailored to the service

⁶¹ George Kakalettris, Eva Sciacca, Jean-Karim Hériché, Wim Hugo, Emanouil Atanasso, & Svetlozar Yordanov. (2023). Design Considerations for Technical Interoperability in EOSC (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8109528> - P.7

provider's capabilities.

In the Appendix n°1, steps to follow are developed for providers who wish to develop a generic SLA including data interoperability. Indeed, the first step before implementing an SLA is to analyse the service provided and the level of guarantees that can be given to users. This is related to human resources management, machine capacity, internal organisation, tests to be carried out to guarantee service levels, incident management, etc. **This analysis work is a first step before committing to any SLAs.**

This implies an analysis of the internal interpretation of data interoperability. This work may lead to a detailed description of how interoperability is currently implemented. When it comes to organisational interoperability, transparency about how the service is delivered is key. The SLA could typically detail how the organisation achieves data interoperability, and this can be incorporated into one section of the SLA or within an attached service description document.

This analytical work will help service providers both to develop the SLA and to start internal work on providing data interoperability, which becomes a virtuous circle.

3.2 MoUs and data interoperability

MoU are useful in different contexts for data interoperability:

- **Establish a framework for data sharing:** the MoU serves as a framework for (meta)data sharing between different entities within a collaboration, such as government agencies, research institutions or private companies. It outlines the terms and conditions under which data will be shared, including formats, standards and protocols for interoperability.
- **Define data governance:** the MoU helps define the governance structure for managing shared data, including the roles and responsibilities of each entity. It establishes protocols for data access, security, quality control, and regulatory compliance to ensure data integrity and confidentiality.
- **Facilitate data integration:** the MoU facilitates within the collaboration the integration of disparate data sources and systems by standardising formats, protocols and interfaces and their implementation. It promotes the harmonisation of data schemas and metadata, enabling seamless interoperability and compatibility between different platforms and applications.
- **Reduce legal and regulatory risks:** the MoU helps mitigate legal and regulatory risks associated with data sharing and exchange by clarifying ownership rights, use permissions, and liability responsibilities. It provides a legal framework for resolving disputes, enforcing compliance and protecting intellectual property.

Overall, a well-drafted MoU in the context of data interoperability promotes transparency, trust and accountability among stakeholders, laying the foundation for effective data governance and collaboration to achieve interoperable data ecosystems.

3.2.1 Results from the test

As with the development of SLAs, a test was launched as part of this deliverable to see if service providers were willing to develop data interoperability MoUs. Out of six organisations contacted, only three completed the questionnaire. As for the test on SLAs, it is acknowledged that the results of this test cannot lead to definitive conclusions as the panel of organisations was not large enough.

Of the three replies received, one organisation offers its services only to researchers (#2), another to both researchers and industry professionals (#1). Finally, one organisation targets researchers, industry professionals and the general public (#3). Two of them have integrated their services into EOSC (#2, #3). All three respondents indicated that their organisation has signed an MoU with other organisations to provide services to the research community.

According to the responses received, only one of the organisations surveyed includes technical details and this is not done through an MoU but, according to their comments, through an SLA (#2) .

Table #19: Results - clauses integrated in the respondents' MoUs

Options included in the MoU	1	2	3
The specification of the format and schemas of the metadata exchanged.		x	
The specification of the format and schemas of the data exchanged.		x	
The assurance of the security, quality and consistency of the data.		x	
Notification of any incidents occurring in the management of the data provided.		x	
Licensing process (for example, maintaining the original licence of the data)		x	
Specification of the response time of any incident		x	
Compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	x	x	x
Inclusion of a termination clause		x	x
Inclusion of a renewal clause		x	

None of the organisations have a data sharing agreement associated with their MoU. All three respondents declare organising periodical meetings with the parties involved in the MoU and all of them declare having signed a contract after use of the MoU.

Their main motivations to sign an MoU are the following:

- Establish an agreed set of activities, opportunities, mutual benefits and exchange of work (#1);
- Develop a firmer connection with similar institutions (#3);
- Get credibility of collaboration (#3);
- Enhance commitment of the parties (#3);

The results of this test show that while some service providers are open to establishing Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) to support data interoperability, there is considerable

variation in the inclusion of technical details and specific clauses. Of the six organisations approached, only three participated, limiting the generalisability of the conclusions.

3.2.2 MoU and data interoperability: suggestion for implementation

As mentioned above, MoUs are used for strategic collaboration rather than technical specifications. While SLAs are designed to manage expectations in service delivery, MoUs outline the terms and details of the mutual understanding or partnership. MoUs tend to be less binding than SLAs, focusing on broader objectives rather than specific service delivery.

This approach is in line with the FAIRsFAIR White Paper⁶². Given that the EOSC federation involves a wide range of organisations, projects and individuals, and the FAIR principles are central to building the EOSC Web of FAIR Data and Services, **data interoperability plays a crucial role in synchronising and aligning the practices of different stakeholders**. This helps to avoid unnecessary duplication of effort by promoting collaboration and pooling initiatives. In this context, data interoperability can be captured in the MoU.

In the context of EOSC and data interoperability, MoUs have several applications. Due to their less binding and service-specific nature, they serve as tools to initiate alignment between stakeholders. Data interoperability in this case can be seen as the alignment of standards across communities. **As EOSC initiatives bring together organisations, service providers and users from different scientific fields and countries, MoUs are instrumental in synchronising their efforts towards a common goal which can be data interoperability.**

This deliverable proposes different options for MoUs and data interoperability:

Figure #3: mapping hypotheses for MoUs for data interoperability

⁶² Dillo, I., Hodson, S., Pittonet Gaiarin, S., & Grootveld, M. (2021). D5.7 Recommendations for a FAIR EOSC - White Paper FAIRsFAIR Synchronisation Force 2021 (Version 1.0 Glossy). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6378823>

Option #1: an MoU to gather all stakeholders working on data interoperability. The aim of this MoU would be **to collectively work on minimum standards to guarantee data interoperability** in the EOSC context at all levels (Legal, Technical, Organisational and Semantic). This would be an intention to work together, have dedicated bodies in order to develop a framework which is in line with all the stakeholders. In that context, the signatories could typically be the EOSC association, the EOSC nodes and the EOSC EU Node. This would allow for a greater integration of the output on the matter.

Option #2: an MoU to structure a governance around data interoperability with the stakeholders working with those standards. It is understood that data interoperability remains an evolving concept. Due to technological advances, innovative contexts, new ways of publishing and structuring data, the standards designed and implemented today may evolve in the future. As the EOSC and European research context engage hundreds of organisations, in case of change, everyone should be kept onboard. By linking the stakeholders with an MoU and a governance with bodies who meet X times a year **to update the standards according to the context, such an agreement would allow adaptability and flexibility to keep on track with good practices** and standards on data interoperability.

Option #3: for EOSC to sign MoUs with other European data spaces. As they may develop their own rules to guarantee data interoperability, MoUs could be a tool to allow the data produced and used among the different European data spaces to be interoperable together by allowing a continuous dialogue among relevant stakeholders. Today, the SIMPL programme is an open source, secure middleware platform that supports data access and interoperability in European data initiatives.⁶³

For all hypotheses developed above, it is important to aim for lightweight and specific MoUs that deal with operational support to implement the cooperation outlined in the agreements.

In the context of this deliverable, as for the SLAs, one template for MoU on data interoperability is not provided as the context of their implementation can be manifold. In the appendix, guidelines of how to develop an MoU on data interoperability are developed. This will help future teams interested in implementing MoU in such a context.

⁶³ SIMPL Programme. [online]. [viewed January 17, 2025]. Available at: <https://simpl-programme.ec.europa.eu/>

Conclusions and next steps

Finally, this deliverable provides guidelines for MoUs and SLAs to define and implement data interoperability within the EOSC Federation context. Given the current transitional phase of EOSC and the lack of established data interoperability guidelines, this deliverable recommends to formulate clear standards through community consultation. This will enable service providers and developers to align themselves with these standards, thereby improving data interoperability.⁶⁴

The guidelines for SLAs and MoUs presented in this deliverable are deliberately designed to be flexible. Their purpose is twofold: firstly, to encourage service providers to articulate how their organisation delivers and, to some extent, guarantees data interoperability to their users; and secondly, to provide a framework that encourages collaboration between relevant stakeholders. This collaborative approach aims to refine the definition of data interoperability and outline its practical implementation.

Moving from fuzzy definitions to clear standards within the EOSC community, backed by agreements, will improve data interoperability and enable a key part of it: organisational interoperability.

⁶⁴ Scardaci Diego Orazio, Sciacca Eva, Hériché Jean-Karim, Van De Sanden Mark, Klaas Wierenga, Manghi Paolo, Tamburri Damian, Mazon Jose Norberto, López García Álvaro, Hugo Wim, Pansanel Jerome, & Krøl Andersen Lene. (2023). A landscape overview of the EOSC Interoperability Framework - Capabilities and Gaps (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8399710>

Appendix 1: Guidelines to develop SLA on data interoperability - based on FitSM

The FitSM standard is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. See www.fitsm.eu for more information.

Objective: to establish a generic SLA including data interoperability

Phase 1: Establish a service management system (SMS) for identified service

Tool to help identify services from FitSM [\[Link\]](#)

Tool to specify a service from FitSM [\[Link\]](#)

Step 1.1- Identify person(s) who will oversee the process, set a deadline and a budget

SMS Owner: is the role that has the overall accountability for the establishment and maintenance of the SMS. By means of effective governance, the SMS owner sets the key goals and provides overall direction for the SMS. Consequently, a person with sufficient authority, usually a person at the top management level, should take on this role.⁶⁵

SMS Manager is the role often regarded as the “project manager” of implementing IT service management in an organisation or federation. However, different from a regular project manager, the SMS manager is not released from their duties after the SMS has been successfully implemented to some extent, since a management system will always require continuing efforts of maintenance, development and improvement. The SMS manager coordinates all efforts in planning, implementing, reviewing and further improving the SMS.⁶⁶

Both roles can follow training from FitSM⁶⁷ to know the process

- + Foundation [\[Link\]](#)
- + Advanced SPD [\[Link\]](#)
- + Advanced SOC [\[Link\]](#)
- + Expert [\[Link\]](#)

Set a deadline and link the following actions to milestones that will feed into the future SMS.

⁶⁵FitSM. FitSM Guidance Document for Role model [online]. FitSM, [n.d.] [viewed November 15, 2024]. Available at: <https://www.fitsm.eu/download/1268/?tmstv=1730964261>- P.3

⁶⁶FitSM. FitSM Guidance Document for Role model [online]. FitSM, [n.d.] [viewed November 15, 2024]. Available at: <https://www.fitsm.eu/download/1268/?tmstv=1730964261> - P.4

⁶⁷ FitSM, Fitsm Downloads, FITSM Training material, online (viewed November 7, 2024): <https://www.fitsm.eu/downloads/#toggle-id-8>

Step 1.2 Test your current processes with FitSM tool: FitSM-6 Capability Maturity Assessment [\[Link\]](#)⁶⁸

This helps to define the scope, the goals and potential targets of the service.

Step 1.3 Develop your SMS based on the general requirements produced by FitSM [\[Link\]](#)

FitSM provides additional support document to help organisations to implement their general requirements [\[Link\]](#)

Step 1.4 Update the SMS in light of data interoperability as a service: how is it guaranteed to users, what are the processes behind?
(To be updated if new guidelines are developed under the EOSC Federation)

1.4.1 Legal interoperability

Global legal context	Legal status of the service provider
	GDPR
	Sectoral regulation
	Competition law
	European legal framework for data sharing
	Law applicable to the Service and its effect on data sharing.
Data access and reuse	Access rights for users from countries other than the country of origin of the data.
	Responsibility for data stored by external users.
	Legal and access conditions for each dataset, made available in a well-known metadata schema and in a machine-readable format.
Metadata	Available without restrictions
	Description of the metadata schema used available.
Licences	Provide clear, standardised licences for datasets, available in both human and machine-readable formats.

⁶⁸ FitSM, Fitsm Downloads, FITSM IMPLEMENTATION AIDS - Maturity / Capacity Assessment Tool, online (viewed November 7, 2024): <https://www.fitsm.eu/downloads/#toggle-id-8>

Step 1.4 Update the SMS in light of data interoperability as a service: how is it guaranteed to users, what are the processes behind?
(To be updated if new guidelines are developed under the EOSC Federation)

	Encourage the use of permissive licences for metadata and data where appropriate, adopting a no-rights-reserved standard (e.g. CC0) where possible.
	Metadata includes information to identify the different components within the dataset, specifying the copyright or licence that applies to each component.
	Mechanism to indicate in the metadata whether copyright has expired or whether the data is already in the public domain.
	Mechanism to indicate in the metadata whether a dataset contains any or all orphan data.
1.4.2 Semantic interoperability	
Use semantic artefacts, such as controlled vocabularies and ontologies	Example of controlled vocabularies (Access rights ⁶⁹ , DCMI ⁷⁰ , DPV ⁷¹ , etc.)
	Example of ontologies: OntoPortal ⁷² , W3C ontologies, Schema.org, SKOS
Robustness of semantic artefacts (SA)	SA based on existing ones and include a usage example
	SA associated with an open licence
	SA are well documented
	SA published in a repository
	SA associated with a PID
	Provide usage recommendations of SA

⁶⁹European Union. Access Right [online]. EU Vocabularies, [n.d.] [viewed October 31, 2024]. Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/dataset/-/resource?uri=http://publications.europa.eu/resource/dataset/access-right>

⁷⁰Dublin Core Metadata Initiative. DCMI Terms [online]. Dublin Core Metadata Initiative, [n.d.] [viewed October 31, 2024]. Available at: <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>

⁷¹Data Privacy Vocabulary Community Group. Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV) [online]. Data Privacy Vocabulary Community Group, [n.d.] [viewed October 31, 2024]. Available at: <https://www.dpvcg.org/>

⁷²OntoPortal. OntoPortal Demo [online]. OntoPortal, [n.d.] [viewed October 31, 2024]. Available at: <https://demo.ontportal.org/>

Step 1.4 Update the SMS in light of data interoperability as a service: how is it guaranteed to users, what are the processes behind?
(To be updated if new guidelines are developed under the EOSC Federation)

Use crosswalks

In case of use of diverse standards = MSCR from FAIRCORE4EOSC⁷³

1.4.3 Technical interoperability

AAI Federation

Adhere to the AAI federation of the federation you belong to via the OAuth protocol or an affiliated one

Harmonise system of roles that can be assigned to users with the federation you adhere to .

Data and metadata formats

Data and metadata are exposed in widely used formats (XML, JSON, CSV and RDF)

Structure defined using JSON or XML schemas to specify fields and attributes of the data exposed

Propose options for conversion into the formats mentioned above

When exposing metadata and data in RDF, resources utilising W3C ontologies, schema.org, SKOMOS, CIDOC CRM or the OntoPortal are used to ensure interoperability through publicly available terms

Search tools

Documentation of how to use API endpoints. Formats such as OpenApi are well known ways of documenting web APIs.

Efficient and well documented search endpoints for their data to allow search to find their data.

PIDs

Managed PID s should be associated with the data shared

PID policy of the organisation should be detailed

1.4.4 Organisational interoperability

SLA structure

If the SLA is well detailed and the FiTSM template is followed, organisational interoperability is enhanced

Limit the number of SLAs produced in relation to one service

Publish a translated version of the SLA in English if applicable.

⁷³ FAIRCORE4EOSC. Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR) [online]. FAIRCORE4EOSC, [n.d.]. Available at: <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/metadata-schema-and-crosswalk-registry-mscr>

Step 1.4 Update the SMS in light of data interoperability as a service: how is it guaranteed to users, what are the processes behind?
(To be updated if new guidelines are developed under the EOSC Federation)

Vocabularies	Use controlled vocabularies to describe services
	Define internal and technical terms used
Service description	Describe how you match all the interoperability levels in the service description.

Phase 2: Draft an SLA drawing from the SMS of your organisation
FitSM Template available online - [\[Link\]](#)⁷⁴

2.1 General – Identification of the parties to the agreement *(should be two parties)*

2.2 Scope and description of the service

2.3 Service availability	Response time
	Potential of failures
	Planned maintenance and upgrades (frequency and duration)

2.4 Service components and dependencies
(Data interoperability provision to be described here)

2.5 Support	Helpdesk: service hours & exceptions
	Incident handling
	Fulfilment of service requests

2.6 Identification of performance metrics & Service level targets	Uptime (time the service runs without interruption)
	Data exchange success rate
	Responsiveness of the teams
	Resolution time
	Usage metrics

2.7 Limitations & Legal *(to be checked with a lawyer)*

⁷⁴ FitSM. Collection of CC-BY 4.0 templates [online]. FitSM, [n.d.] [viewed October 31, 2024]. Available at: <https://www.fitsm.eu/downloads/#toggle-id-5>

Phase 2: Draft an SLA drawing from the SMS of your organisation
FitSM Template available online - [\[Link\]](#) ⁷⁴

constraints	Technical (<i>storage capacity, etc</i>)
2.8 Communication with users	Communication channels with users are publicly available
	Detailed documentation on the service provision
	Service roadmap exist and shared with users
2.9 SLA violations / penalties	Information to users
	Escalation and complaints
	Compensation to occur in case of failure
2.10. Information security & data protection	
2.11. Responsibilities	Additional responsibilities of the service provider
	Customer responsibilities
2.12 Monitoring and reporting	Tracking tools
	Reporting frequency
	Incident logging
2.13 Continuous improvement	Regular reviews
	Capacity of adjustment
2.14 Additional information	Glossary of terms
	Document control

Phase 3: English Translation of the SLA if applicable

Phase 4: review and approval	3.1 Internal – with teams
	3.2: External – with users
	3.3 External – with lawyer(s)
	3.4 External – EOSC Federation representatives

Phase 5: signature of the SLA	Can be shared on the websites of the service provider
	Directly shared with users with signatures from both parties

Appendix 2: Guidelines to develop MoU on data interoperability

Objective: to establish an MoU for data interoperability

Phase 1 - Framework	1.1 Identify a person in each participating organisation who will be responsible for overseeing the MoU development process.
	1.2 Nominate a team and define roles and responsibilities according to the different skills of the people involved in the project.
	1.3 Set a deadline and link the following actions to milestones that will feed into the future MoU.
	1.4 If necessary, set up a budget for the preparatory phase of the MoU

Phase 2- Introduction / Purpose of the MoU	2.1 Identify relevant stakeholders and conduct consultations	EOSC Federation Nodes ; EOSC Association ; European Commission ; experts; etc. <i>⇒can be 2 or more than 2 parties</i>
	2.2 Background analysis	Lacks, existing standards, technical capabilities Tool: use cases, user needs of the designated community
	2.3 Define objectives	Why is this MoU necessary? What is the sought value? To what degree should the agreement be legally binding?

Phase 3 – Definitions	3.1 Define the technical and operational aspects of the service / tool or process developed
	3.2 Define the community-specific terms and acronyms

Phase 4 - Address technical and operational considerations	4.1 Identify the end users and their needs	In what context do data need to be interoperable? Are there differences between communities or in regulation?
	4.2 Technical and semantic interoperability	Definition of how standards will be defined in the context of the MoU. Description of the process followed. Example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyse data users needs and describe the users process Identify current guidelines and good practices implemented in the communities Collect recommendations from experts Identification of possible conflicts with relevant regulations and policies Pilot and test solutions
	4.3 Legal and organisational interoperability	

Phase 5 - Distribution of responsibilities and collaboration mechanisms	5.1 Who is in charge of overseeing the MoU?	Role based, Organisations and eventually specific bodies
	5.2 Who is in charge of the different actions described in the MoU?	Role based, Organisations and eventually specific bodies
	5.3 Identification of dependencies among the stakeholders	
	5.4 Definition of collaboration mechanisms	Establish channels for ongoing communication among stakeholders to facilitate collaboration

Phase 6: Timeline and milestones	6.1 Define a starting date and an end date
	6.2 Definition of milestones
	6.3 Define updates and amendment process
	6.4 Describe the conditions of termination of the agreement

Phase 7: writing of the MoU including all steps described before
(1) Preamble ; (2) Definitions ; (3) Objectives ; (4) Roles and responsibilities ; (5) Timeline and milestones ; (6) Collaboration mechanisms

Phase 8: English Translation of the MoU if applicable

Phase 9: Review	9.1: Internal	Strategy team
	9.2: External	Consult legal experts (Lawyers / Legal department) to ensure that the MoU is relevant according to laws and regulations and address intellectual property rights
		All potential signatories of the MoU

Phase 10: Signature of the MoU

Appendix 3: Other data interoperability contracts

Name	Description	Topics typically covered	Use with Interoperability
ToU	<p>Terms of Use, also referred to as ‘Terms of Service’, ‘Terms and Conditions’ or ‘User Agreement’.</p> <p>Depicts the services the provider is offering the end user, and outlines the responsibilities of them as users of the service.</p> <p>To ensure enforceability, it should be made obligatory to consent to the ToU before using the service. By agreeing to the terms of use, users acknowledge their responsibility for adhering to these terms and any potential breaches.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User rights and responsibilities, authentication • Intellectual property & Privacy policy • Disclaimers • Limitation of liability⁷⁵. <p>The precise details will differ based on the characteristics of the service.</p>	<p>Similar to SLAs, describe in a user-friendly way how data interoperability is provided and what the user can expect from the service.</p>
DSA	<p>A DSAData Sharing Agreement is a detailed and technical document that specifies how data will be shared between two or more parties.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parties concerned • Purpose of data sharing • Definition of key terms • Organisations involved in data sharing • Types of data shared + Data quality and liability • Access and data transfer methods • Legal basis for sharing data and using data • Privacy and security requirements • Retention, return and deletion of data • Termination and modification 	<p>Can be used to detail how data interoperability is guaranteed. It helps to clarify the conditions under which data are shared and used. Such a document can complement an MoU or an SLA.</p>

⁷⁵Cambridge Dictionary. Terms [online]. Cambridge University Press, [n.d.] [accessed October 31, 2024]. Available at: <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/terms?q=Terms>